

TEACHING PRIMARY GRADES TO READ WITHOUT MISTAKES AND THE ROLE OF PARENTS IN THIS PROCESS

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Abstract. In this thesis, it is about how to teach elementary school students to read expressively, to pronounce words correctly, divide them into syllables correctly, and to express their speech freely.

Keywords: expressive reading, word, syllable, pronunciation, speech.

INTRODUCTION

Primary education is the most important and complex link of the continuous education system. Teaching expressive reading in primary grades is the development of oral and written speech of reading content by classes. It is necessary to conduct the training. When a child comes to school, he first learns to read and write. Little by little, he begins to choose a book independently, the skills of being able to correctly evaluate the book he has read are formed. In the elementary grades, students should be able to divide words into the correct syllables, so the teacher should work with each student and deal with the students correctly. Expressive reading plays a key role for the teacher as one of the known methods of thorough mastering of various artistic and practical texts. In expressive reading lessons, it does not allow students to get bored, on the contrary, it activates them, increases their interest in works of art, and arouses admiration for literature. Children's literary pronunciation norms are formed in the process of expressive reading and interactive speech activity.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Correct use of grammatical forms of students' speech and correct pronunciation will help children's speech to be fluent and expressive. In expressive reading [1]:

- a) ability to use breath correctly;
- b) good knowledge of literary language pronunciation norms; c) correct and accurate pronunciation of words, syllables and sounds;

These 3 rules should be followed in expressive teaching of elementary school students. Teaching expressive reading in the elementary grades, every student can pronounce words correctly, separate syllables correctly, and read at a normal speed, understands the content. When normalizing the child's reading speed, he should pay attention to 2 things [2]:

1. Show sample reading at normal speed;
2. Check by giving assignments so that the reading inside is not superficial.

RESULTS

Among such main goals of the primary education content, one can include teaching students to learn independently, strengthening expressiveness, forming a worldview, independent and expressive work. In order for students to master the fundamentals of the subject they are studying in the process of primary education, we should first of all equip them with the skills and abilities of independent thinking and observation," he says. At the elementary school level, extracurricular reading classes have an important educational value

in teaching students to read independently and expressively. It is the duty of every pedagogue to teach students expressively and create skills in primary grades.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Expressiveness means expressiveness. Expressive reading is the first and main form of clear and visual teaching of literature. The teacher visually conveys the content and emotionality of the work to the students through expressive reading. Reading classes have a special place among other educational subjects with features that develop students' thinking and speech, as well as comprehensively develop students' personalities. In the process of reading lessons, students' reading skills improve, and their ability to understand the idea of an artistic work of reading correctly, consciously, and expressively grows. In the 2nd grade of the textbook of mother tongue and reading literacy, part 1, section 1, the following story on the topic "When I grow up, I will get the Nobel Prize!" helps to educate, preserve nature, and help students to achieve their goals. My name is Muhammad, my last name is Haydarov. I study in the second grade. I am interested in strange things in nature. That's why my favorite subject is natural sciences. There are many mysteries in nature.

I am amazed when I read about how simple rain or wind is created. I especially want to know more about the stars and planets in the sky. When I grow up, I will be an astronomer. I work in cooperation with organizations such as NASA and SpaceX. I will help them explore the universe. I make spaceships myself. In them, astronauts fly to the Moon and Mars. To become a good astronomer, you need to study all subjects with excellent grades. Physics, mathematics and chemistry should be studied in depth. Because if we fly to other galaxies, we will need this knowledge.

I want to win the Nobel Prize in the future. Uzbek scientists have not yet received this award. I may be the first Uzbek to receive the Nobel Prize. For this, it is necessary to do a great work that will benefit all people. I know it's not easy. But I will definitely try. In the 2nd grade, students develop the skills of reading the entire word, and the desire for correct, expressive reading is clearly felt. He tries to read some texts independently without making a sound. They quickly understand the texts taught with the help of the teacher, they try to express some of the events in them through words. In the process of reading and speaking, students are required to follow the norms of the literary language. Students are taught several times on the basis of various specific tasks and the responsibility of studying is increased.

In reading classes, it is necessary to allocate the main part of the lesson to students' reading. The head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his speech, reflected on education:

CONCLUSIONS

"The quality, content, and environment of education will not change if the teaching methodology in the school does not change." In conclusion, every teacher should work together with students to create tomorrow's future. It is necessary to instill in children a love for books, to teach them to use books, to get the necessary knowledge from them, that is, to cultivate readers who know how to work with books, think deeply, and think carefully. For this, teachers should love their profession and approach it with responsibility. Students should be able to pronounce words and letters correctly and divide them into syllables. For this, we should encourage students to love books and read books. The more books readers read, the more we can achieve our goal.

References:

1. Oripov, B. T. "Ways to improve the effectiveness of lessons" Tashkent 2013
2. ЕРМАТОВА, Р. О. (2018). УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ВРЕМЕННЫМ УЧЕНИЕМ ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВ С ОБУЧЕНИЕМ ИНВАЛИДЫ. Наука среди нас, (7), 85-88.
3. Ermatova, R. O. (2018). ADVANTAGES OF THE TECHNIQUE "WHAT/HOW/WHY OUTLINES" IN DEVELOPING PRODUCTIVE SKILLS OF THE MEDICAL STUDENTS. Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук, (6), 69-71.
4. Utegenova, S., & Rozumova, D. (2024). DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING TAX AUDIT. Modern Science and Research, 3(6).
5. Utegenova, S., & Mirzabaeva, U. (2024). TODAY'S IMPORTANCE AND PROSPECTS OF AUDIT ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 4(6), 93-95.
6. Utegenova, S., & Oralbaeva, F. (2024). O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotiga xorijiy investitsiyalar oqimini oshirishda mamlakatning investitsion muhiti jozibadorligini oshirish. Журнал академических исследований нового Узбекистана, 1(6), 131-134.
7. Khasanova, S., Akisheva, N., & Zholayeva, M. (2023). Methodological aspects of tax planning in the context of sustainable development. Revista Gestão & Tecnologia, 23(3), 286-298.
8. Маматқулов, Б. М., & Нематов, А. А. (2021). Ўзбекистон Республикаси аҳолиси орасида COVID-19 тарқалишининг хусусиятлари.
9. Abdullayeva, N. (2023). AHMAD YASSAWI SECT: THE ISSUE OF ZIKR AND THE STATUS OF ZAKIR. Modern Science and Research, 2(5), 438-440.
10. Bazarov, S. (2024). JURNALIST VA BLOGERLAR NUTQI ETIKASI. Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика, 3(1), 36-39.
11. Norqulovich, S. H. (2023, October). NURILLO CHORINING BADIY ASARLARIDA MILLIY KOLORITGA XOS KO 'RINISHLAR NUTQIY JIHATDAN IFODALANISHI. In International conference on multidisciplinary science (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 25-29).
12. Ziyodullayeva, M., & Muxtorova, M. (2024). ABDULLA QODIRIY HAYOTI VA IJODIGA AYRIM CHIZGILAR. NRJ, 1(3), 860-863.
13. Muxtorova, M. (2024). MAXTUMQULI SHE'RIYATIDA AYTISHUV: AN'ANA VA IZDOSHLIK. NRJ, 1(3), 254-257.
14. Tajenova, G., Turdiyeva, G., Qurbanov, A., & Isakov, I. (2020). Current state and development of agricultural products exports of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Архив научных исследований, (14).
15. Janabay, I., Gulbahar, T., Gulayda, T., Alisher, Q., & Ilkhambek, I. (2020). Current state and development of agricultural products exports of the republic of uzbekistan. International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation, 24(8), 1684-1693.
16. Turdieva, G., Abishov, M., & Muratbaev, I. (2024). THE IMPACT OF CREDIT RISKS ON AN EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION IN THE FINANCIAL SERVICES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS. NRJ, 1(4), 215-225.
17. Beglenov, N., & Muratbaev, I. (2023). HOTEL SERVICES AS AN OBJECT OF STRATEGIC MARKETING ORIENTED TO THE CONSUMER. Science and Education in Karakalpakstan, 32(2), 175-177.
18. Xalmuratovich, B. S. (2024). JAHON AMALIYOTIDA AGROKLASTER TIZIMINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISH VA YURITISH BO 'YICHA TO 'PLANGAN TAJRIBALAR TAHLILI. Scientific Journal of Actuarial Finance and Accounting, 4(04), 140-150.

19. Bayjanov, S. X., & Abishov, M. S. (2024). DEVELOPING THE ACTIVITY OF JOINT STOCK COMPANIES BY IMPROVING DIVIDEND POLICY. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 3(3), 94-97.

20. Sultanov, B., Nurimbetov, T., Bayjanov, S., Seyilbekov, B., & Durmanov, A. (2023, October). Trends in change and the current state of the effectiveness of land reclamation measures in agriculture. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2921, No. 1). AIP Publishing.

